

Da'wah In Addressing Environmental Health Issue In Bontonyelang Village, Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to identify the forms and synergy of da'wah used to address environmental health issues in Bontonyelang Village, Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. This research employs a qualitative approach with a focus on da'wah communication. The data sources for this study consist of primary and secondary data, which are analyzed using data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The findings indicate that the forms of da'wah utilized to address environmental health in Bontonyelang Village include tabligh (conveying religious messages), irsyad (guidance), tadbir (management), and tamkin (empowerment). This da'wah initiative is a collaborative program involving Islamic preachers (dai), the village head, the Family Welfare Empowerment group, and healthcare workers from Bontonyelang Community Health Center (Puskesmas). The synergy in implementing this da'wah has had a positive impact on shifting community paradigms and behaviors, as seen in the reduction of domestic waste disposal into irrigation channels. Additionally, approximately 15 out of 50 households have adopted environmentally friendly practices by establishing waste bins. It is hoped that the da'wah approach in addressing environmental health issues in Bontonyelang Village can be comprehensively applied by the residents and serve as a reference for tackling environmental health concerns in other communities.

Keywords: Da'wah, Environmental Health.

INTRODUCTION

The development of da'wah in Indonesia marks a significant evolution from time to time, especially with the emergence of modernization that affects the way humans interact with space and time (Ghofur, 2019). In this context, da'wah not only functions as a means of spreading religious teachings, but also as an instrument to address various social problems, including environmental health issues. In the midst of technological advances and globalization, environmental problems such as climate change, pollution, and ecosystem degradation are increasingly urgent to overcome. Da'wah, with the right approach, can be a transformative force in mobilizing people to care and act in preserving the environment (Aziz, 2014).

Da'wah has a central role in shaping the behavior of people who care about the environment, so that environmental health can be maintained optimally (Pribadi et al., 2023). Da'wah not only plays a role in conveying religious messages, but also as an agent of social change that can mobilize people to act in preserving the environment (Apridamayanti et al., 2023). The community has the responsibility to maintain and preserve the surrounding environment (Indra, 2019). Da'wah activities can be carried out in various forms, whether through oral, real action, or writing, all of which aim to invite humans to practice Islamic teachings comprehensively (Toni et al., 2022).

The level of concern of the Indonesian people for environmental health and hygiene is still very low, so the government, religious leaders, community leaders, youth leaders, and students play an important role in providing socialization or understanding of the importance of maintaining environmental cleanliness (Sentana, 2018). The low public awareness of environmental hygiene is reflected in littering behavior, which is considered a serious problem because it can cause flooding and other health problems (Chaniago et al., 2023). This condition also worsens when facilities or recycling of plastic waste are inadequate, so this triggers environmental pollution such as water, air and soil pollution. Active

participation from various elements of society is needed to increase awareness of the importance of protecting the environment, which will also have a positive impact on overall public health (Anwar & Wibowo, 2021).

An environmental health approach that integrates religious values is essential, considering that religion has a strong influence in shaping people's behavior and ethics (Wardiha, 2018). Integrating da'wah messages with environmental issues can increase public awareness about the importance of protecting nature as a mandate from God Almighty. Da'wah efforts in overcoming environmental problems must be carried out creatively and innovatively, especially in the era of media convergence. Da'wah is no longer limited to lectures in taklim assemblies, but also utilizes various media such as television and other digital platforms (Wijaya et al., 2019).

Transformative efforts to improve the environmental and community health of Bontonyeleng Village have been implemented through collaboration between village officials, religious shops, PKK and health service units. Through a holistic and inclusive program, the community is educated on Clean and Healthy Living Behaviors through various media of communication, news delivery, and transformative education. These initiatives include effective waste management, proper sanitation, and sustainable personal hygiene practices.

Various methods have been implemented with a focus on maintaining environmental health. The practices carried out are education on the management of plastic waste into crafts, environmental health seminars, planting family medicinal plants (TOGA) and a culture of mutual cooperation in cleaning the environment regularly. The culture of gotong royong is an inherent characteristic of the Indonesian nation. This culture has been ingrained even into the nation's personality and culture that has been deeply rooted in the lives of Indonesian people since time immemorial. This effort intends to maintain ecosystems, develop conservation strategies, and maintain ecosystem functions and services for local communities (GUIDELINES FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH ACTION ON TROPICAL FOREST 2024 (CRA FOREST 2024), 2024).

However, the reality is that even though mutual cooperation has been carried out, there is still community apathy regarding environmental cleanliness. Based on data from the Ministry of Environment and Forestry in 2020, Indonesia produced up to 67.8 million tons of waste with the highest composition of waste, in the form of food waste, which is 39.8%. As reported by The Economist Intelligence Unit, in 2017 Indonesia was ranked second as the largest contributor of waste after Saudi Arabia with a total waste produced of 13 tons per year, which when averaged with the population at that time, each person contributed 300kg of food waste per year (Kairiyah, 2021).

Based on this fact, da'wah can be a solution that provides a deep understanding of the importance of protecting the environment from a religious perspective, thus raising spiritual awareness and moral responsibility in each individual. Individual awareness of the environment can be increased in various ways, one of which is through a religious approach (2021-09-23Bappenas-Development of Compress Swamp Management.Pdf, n.d.).

Da'wah has an important role in shaping public awareness and behavior towards the environment, especially in household waste management (Nasrudin et al., 2020). Through the right da'wah approach, people can be invited to participate and care more about the environment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is qualitative with a da'wah communication approach and is conducted in Bontonyeleng Village. The data collection methods used include observation, interviews, and documentation. The data processing and analysis techniques follow three stages: data reduction, data presentation, and data verification and conclusion drawing.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Da'wah is fundamentally about inviting all of humanity to adopt good behavior, transforming negative actions into positive ones, and advocating for positive change to improve both physical and spiritual well-being across the world. Da'wah must be continuous, as it carries a sacred mandate and moral responsibility that should be upheld persistently to achieve a society of rahmatan lil 'alamin (a mercy to all creation).

The implementation of Islamic da'wah serves as a government initiative in collaboration with religious leaders, the Family Welfare Empowerment group (PKK), and healthcare institutions to address environmental health issues in Bontonyeleng Village. This approach integrates da'wah methods, including tabligh (religious communication), irsyad (guidance), tadbir (management), and tamkin (empowerment).

FORMS OF DA'WAH IN ADDRESSING ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH ISSUES IN BONTONYELENG VILLAGE.

1. *Tabligh in the Form of Sermons and Religious Studies*

Tabligh is essentially a continuous da'wah activity that must be carried out by Muslims throughout their lives. However, in practice, tabligh can take on various characteristics—it may be incidental, oral, mass-oriented, ceremonial, or even colossal, depending on specific situations and conditions (Marlida, 2022).

Regarding tabligh methods, if we refer to the definition and examples set by Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), there are two main approaches: tabligh through speech and tabligh through writing. Tabligh through speech involves the dissemination of Islamic values orally, whether in the context of ritual worship (ibadah mahdah) or social worship (ibadah ghairu mahdah).

In an effort to spread da'wah messages, the village head and Islamic preachers (dai) have implemented various da'wah approaches to address environmental health issues in Bontonyeleng Village. These efforts include bil-lisan (oral da'wah), such as incorporating environmental health topics into Friday sermons and Maulid Nabi Muhammad (PBUH) celebrations, as well as bil-qalam (written da'wah) by installing posters and signboards in public areas, schools, and marketplaces. The written messages include “Do Not Litter Here,” “Dispose of Waste Properly,” and “If You Are a True Believer, Do Not Litter Here” to encourage environmental awareness and responsible waste management within the community.

a. **Regular Sermons by Islamic Preachers on the Importance of Environmental Health**

A sermon is a form of religious activity generally organized to provide understanding of religion, morality, and life values to the community. It creates a space for spiritual reflection, personal growth, and faith strengthening, contributing to the formation of a virtuous society with awareness of noble values.

In addressing environmental health issues, sermons delivered by Islamic preachers (dai) in Bontonyeleng Village provide a deep understanding of the vital role of environmental cleanliness in maintaining health and collective well-being. This program is conducted regularly once a month in different mosques within the area.

The community actively participates in these sermons, showing high enthusiasm through an initiative called the rotating charity box (celengan bergilir), introduced by the women of the religious study group (majelis taklim). The box is filled during each sermon session, and the collected funds are managed by the leader of the religious study group. These funds are used to purchase refreshments, such as snacks and drinking water, for the next sermon session.

However, it is important to recognize that implementation in the field faces significant challenges, as inherent human behavioral tendencies often lead to apathy toward cleanliness and environmental health, which has been ingrained from an early age. In practice, sermons delivered by Islamic preachers (dai) are sometimes perceived merely as informational talks rather than internalized lessons by the community. This is evident when, despite hearing the message, some individuals leave the gathering without properly disposing of their waste, demonstrating a lack of immediate behavioral change.

Addressing this issue requires sustained efforts, consistency in message delivery, and a deeper understanding of the urgency and positive impact that environmental awareness can bring to the community.

b. **Regular Religious Studies by Islamic Preachers on the Importance of Physical Cleanliness and Environmental Health**

One of the aspects that reflect the perfection and beauty of Islam is how it regulates both acts of worship (ubudiyah) and humanitarian aspects (insaniyah). Islam not only emphasizes ritual worship to Allah SWT but also gives great attention to human well-being, including public health as a supporting factor in performing worship. Through regular religious studies (pengajian) conducted by Islamic preachers (dai) in Bontonyeleng Village, the community is encouraged to

understand and apply these principles, fostering a culture of care and awareness toward personal health and environmental well-being.

The material covers various aspects, from ablution (wudhu) and major ritual purification (mandi besar) to the techniques of dry ablution (tayammum) and proper cleansing after defecation (istinja'). Additionally, strong emphasis is placed on the importance of maintaining environmental health through simple actions, such as proper waste disposal and avoiding open defecation in irrigation channels—not only to prevent environmental pollution but also to instill a sense of shame within the community.

It has been observed that the irrigation river in Bontonyeleng Village lacks emergency toilet facilities, such as those made from tarpaulin or recycled wood, leading some residents to use a sarong to squat by the riverbank when defecating. This practice often creates discomfort for passersby. After defecation, some villagers cleanse themselves by submerging in the river, while only a few use a water dipper (gayung). This situation highlights the urgent need to raise public awareness, as Islam has already outlined proper methods for purification (istinja') to ensure both personal hygiene and environmental cleanliness.

2. *Irsyad in the Form of Guidance and Counseling*

Linguistically, irsyad means guidance, counseling, or instruction. Meanwhile, in terminology, irsyad refers to conveying Islamic teachings through counseling, guidance, or Islamic psychotherapy to individuals or small groups in a setting that fosters closeness between the counselor and the recipient (Umro'atin, 2019).

In the context of Islam, irsyad often refers to religious guidance or instruction in understanding and practicing Islamic teachings. This guidance is typically provided by scholars (ulama), teachers, or religious figures who have the expertise to offer direction and explanations regarding religious principles, ethics, and worship practices. The primary goal of irsyad is to assist individuals or communities in attaining a proper understanding of Islam and implementing its teachings correctly in their daily lives.

One form of dakwah carried out by health service institution employees in Desa Bontonyeleng is irsyad dakwah, which has been actualized through environmental dakwah movements. This initiative begins with counseling sessions aimed at raising public awareness about the importance of maintaining health and environmental cleanliness. Health counseling is considered a crucial first step and an effective approach, as knowledge about healthy practices and efforts to maintain a clean environment serves as the foundation for community well-being. The Puskesmas staff, along with PKK members, play a key role in identifying environmental health risks.

a. Sanitation Counseling

Sanitation is a series of actions carried out by the Bontonyeleng Community Health Center (Puskesmas) staff to prevent, control, and reduce the risk of disease transmission through the environment. The majority of Bontonyeleng Village residents rely on wells as their primary water source. This condition poses potential health risks, particularly related to digestion, as some drinking water sources are not supplied by the regional water utility (PDAM), which offers more reliable water quality. Additionally, during the dry season, residents' wells often dry up, forcing them to use wells in rice fields and irrigation canals as alternatives for daily activities such as bathing, washing clothes, washing dishes, and even defecating.

Data on the Number of Bontonyeleng Village Residents Diagnosed with Diseases Due to an Unclean Environment.

Types of Diseases	Total
Diarrhea	120
Upper Respiratory Tract Infection (URTI)	21
Tetanus	5
Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF)	11
Malaria	10
Typhoid Fever	48
Skin Disease (Chickenpox)	50
Filariasis	3

Source of Data: Bontonyeleng Community Health Center

The table above illustrates various diseases resulting from the local residents' negligence toward their surrounding environment. This phenomenon includes a lack of awareness regarding the importance of proper sanitation practices, such as the use of clean water sources, which trigger the emergence of various diseases. If left unaddressed, these health issues could negatively impact both public health and the image of Bontonyeleng Village. Sanitation counseling and inspections of residents' sanitation facilities are conducted by community health center staff two to three times a year. However, it is important to note that the presence of the Bontonyeleng Community Health Center within the residential area, along with the collaboration led by the village head to address environmental health issues, has had a positive impact in reducing the prevalence of diseases caused by low community participation in implementing sanitation awareness programs.

b. Counseling on Clean and Healthy Living Behavior.

The state of being healthy is not obtained effortlessly but must be consistently pursued, transforming an unhealthy lifestyle into a healthy one while creating a clean and safe environment. This understanding should be instilled in children from an early age as a long-term investment in raising awareness of the importance of maintaining personal and environmental health. The counseling sessions are held in elementary and Islamic junior high school classrooms, as well as in the Bontonyeleng village office. Clean and Healthy Living Behavior counseling in Bontonyeleng Village is conducted regularly every six months to ensure program effectiveness, followed by handwashing practice with soap and the distribution of vitamin C to all students participating in the session. Additionally, evaluations are conducted through interviews and direct surveys at residents' homes to assess the extent to which the previously delivered materials have been applied in daily life.

2. Tamkin in the Form of Mentorship and Community Empowerment

According to language, *tahwir* or *tamkin* means development, while in terminology, it refers to an implementative da'wah activity through charitable action movements such as human and environmental empowerment. *Dakwah tahwir* can be carried out through educational programs, training, empowerment, village mentoring, economic development, and the provision of educational and religious infrastructure. (Sukayat, 2015).

The da'wah paradigm of community development prioritizes action over discourse or rhetoric, making it an essential approach in the context of Islamic development. This paradigm positions da'wah as a form of struggle aimed at revitalizing the prophetic spirit of Islam and realizing the role of scholars in fundamentally transforming society through historical, cultural, and structural approaches with a people-oriented, practical method. (Umro'atin, 2019). *Tamkin* can be implemented through charitable movements such as human and environmental empowerment in addressing environmental health issues in Bontonyeleng Village. The assistance provided by the village head, in collaboration with PKK members, *dai*, and health center staff, includes planting family medicinal plants, managing plastic waste into handicrafts, mutual cooperation, making signs, and more. This program, initiated by the government, aims to enhance community self-reliance by utilizing both human and natural resources available in Bontonyeleng Village.

a. Assistance in Managing Plastic Waste into Handicrafts

Crafting from plastic waste is an attractive business option. The use of plastic waste in daily life continues to increase, making the problem more complex. The training program organized by the PKK aims to enhance women's skills through the utilization of plastic waste. This initiative has great potential, not only in improving their practical abilities but also in creating a positive economic impact through the handicraft products they produce.

The majority of women in Bontonyeleng Village work as housewives, making this training highly beneficial in helping them utilize their free time, which was previously spent solely on household chores. Additionally, through training in plastic waste management for handicrafts, women and children can contribute positively to the cleanliness of their living environment.

In addition to enhancing the capacity for managing plastic waste into handicrafts, the PKK also provides guidance on utilizing social media, particularly Facebook Marketplace, for business promotion. This is highly relevant in today's digital era, as many modern housewives in Bontonyeleng Village enjoy shopping online. Although the social media utilization assistance is limited, it is expected to have a positive impact on improving the local economy.

b. Assistance in Planting Family Medicinal Plants.

The assistance in planting family medicinal plants in Bontonyeleng Village is an initiative aimed at enhancing understanding, utilization, and skills in improving the health standards of the local community. This is crucial given that the people of Bontonyeleng Village still adhere to traditional customs and beliefs regarding the usefulness and effectiveness of plants as an alternative treatment for disease prevention and cure.

The residents of Bontonyeleng Village utilize their home yards not only to plant various ornamental flowers but also to cultivate Family Medicinal Plants, vegetables, and fruits. For example, they grow moringa trees as yard fences, as well as rambutan and mango trees. Additionally, they plant chili, tomatoes, ginger, and lemongrass. Through the mentoring program conducted by PKK members, the community gains a better understanding of yard management. Planting ornamental flowers and TOGA not only enhances the aesthetic appeal of their surroundings but also provides diverse natural resources beneficial to family health. The use of moringa trees as yard fences also reflects creativity in optimizing limited space for functional purposes while maintaining environmental sustainability.

c. Mutual Cooperation

The preaching movement in the form of *tabligh* is a dakwah effort that prioritizes verbal communication as the main medium, with the goal of bringing about change. This movement begins by encouraging all residents to actively maintain environmental cleanliness as an expression of their commitment to Islamic teachings, which are deeply rooted in the local community. In its implementation, this movement not only calls on people to clean their surroundings but also educates them on the relationship between environmental cleanliness and human health. It aims to address issues such as scattered waste, improper household garbage disposal, and the dumping of livestock waste into river streams.

The cleaning of the irrigation river in Bontonyeleng Village is known as *mappaenre'*, a communal activity carried out by residents to maintain and preserve the river's function. The implementation of *mappaenre'* involves the participation of the entire village community. This activity includes several stages, such as clearing grass growing along the riverbanks, trimming tree branches extending into the irrigation channel, and removing fallen branches carried by the river current that may obstruct the water flow. Each resident participating in this activity brings tools such as hoes, machetes, sickles, and other necessary equipment.

Additionally, the women of Bontonyeleng Village also play a role by bringing food such as rice, coffee, and cakes to be consumed during break time. Before the communal work begins, the village head instructs the neighborhood leaders (RT/RW) to announce the activity at the mosque, usually after the *Subuh* prayer, with the information being repeated around 6 AM. Residents are also informed to bring the necessary cleaning tools to ensure the smooth execution of the communal work. The participation of the entire community in *mappaenre'* reflects the spirit of cooperation and a collective awareness of the importance of maintaining the environment and irrigation infrastructure for daily life in Bontonyeleng Village.

d. Making "Keep Clean" Signs

The creation of signs is a manifestation of *dakwah bil-lisan* integrated with visual messages to convey religious values to the community. Through the initiative of making "Keep Clean" signs led by the village head along with the residents of Bontonyeleng Village, there has been a gradual shift in community habits, reducing the tendency to dispose of waste into the irrigation stream. This progress is evident from the decreasing number of households that channel wastewater from dishwashing and bathrooms directly into the irrigation river. Field surveys and interviews indicate that 15 out of 50 households have transitioned to more environmentally friendly practices by constructing wastewater collection tanks for

dishwashing. This demonstrates that collaboration between the village head, religious preachers, and local residents can significantly contribute to efforts in maintaining health and environmental sustainability.

Several complaints from the community, directly conveyed to the head of Bontonyeleng Village, have raised awareness of the urgency of environmental health issues. In response to this challenge, concrete measures were taken through the creation of slogans and signs. The purpose of installing signs with messages such as "No Littering Here" and "Keep Clean" is to inform the public that these areas are not designated for waste disposal. This effort aims to provide a visual solution and widely accepted message to address the concrete issues faced by the Bontonyeleng Village community. Additionally, the initiative of creating slogans and signs seeks to instill a sense of *siri* (shame) among the residents. This has been a major obstacle, as the lack of shame in engaging in negative actions and the tendency to take pride in improper behavior have contributed to the problem. Shame is closely linked to faith; the two complement each other like two sides of a coin that cannot be separated.

The collaboration between the village head and the *dai* in addressing environmental health issues in Bontonyeleng Village demonstrates an effective partnership between religious leaders and the local government in improving environmental conditions. Through this cooperation, the *dai* acts as an intermediary in communicating religious values, such as the importance of maintaining environmental cleanliness, to the community through sermons and religious gatherings. Meanwhile, the village head serves as a bridge between the government and the community, ensuring that policies supporting environmental health are properly implemented and adhered to by all residents of Bontonyeleng Village.

Based on an interview with Martini AT, a resident of Bontonyeleng Village, she stated:

"With the collaboration between the dai and the village head, we have gained a better understanding of how Islam places great emphasis on human health." (Martini, Interview, April 16, 2024).

From the explanation above, the researcher found that the collaboration between the *dai* and the village head through sermons and religious studies in addressing environmental health issues in Bontonyeleng Village is a long-term investment in saving the planet. This initiative is carried out to ensure that the beauty of nature and environmental well-being are well preserved so that future generations can still enjoy the serene village atmosphere with vast rice fields and clean irrigation channels.

The *dai* does not only focus on how the community maintains the environment through communal work and proper waste disposal but also strives to teach and instill ethical values toward the environment. This is because humans play a crucial role in preserving and protecting the ecosystem as a key to sustaining human life. Additionally, the *dai* also teaches the community about the importance of personal hygiene by applying the concept of *thaharah*, including *wudu*, purification from *junub*, and *istinja'*.

Through sermons and religious gatherings, the *dai* not only teaches the importance of maintaining environmental cleanliness but also instills values of purity and cleanliness as integral aspects of religious practice and daily life. Thus, the *dai* does not solely focus on the physical aspects of health but also acknowledges the significance of spiritual cleanliness in maintaining holistic balance and well-being for individuals and the community.

CONCLUSION

The form of *dakwah* in addressing environmental health issues in Desa Bontonyeleng has led to significant changes in both the paradigm and behavior of the community. The village head, *dai*, PKK, and healthcare workers from Community Health Center Bontonyeleng utilize *dakwah tabligh* through sermons and religious gatherings, as well as *dakwah irsyad* through guidance and environmental health counseling. These efforts aim to cultivate awareness and a sense of responsibility among the community towards their surroundings. To ensure that the health messages conveyed are well understood and implemented in daily life, a mix of Indonesian and Bugis languages is used in the communication process.

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